

The Role of Innovation in the Tourist Attitude and Improving the Destination Performance

(Case study: visitors of historical places in Tehran)

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to investigate the role of innovation in the tourist attitude and improve the performance of the destination. In this regard, while reviewing the concepts of innovation, tourist attitude, and destination performance, using the structural equation modeling method, we examined the effect of innovation on tourist attitude and promotion of destination performance. The statistical population of this study includes tourists from historical places in Tehran, whose number is unlimited. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie-Morgan 384 sample size determination table, which was selected using simple random sampling. In order to collect data in this research, a questionnaire was used, the validity of which was confirmed as content validity by experts, and the validity of construction and structure by confirmatory factor analysis in Smart-pls software and its reliability using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, approved by a factor of 0.954. In order to analyze the data in this study, the Chlomogroff-Smirnov test was used for regular testing, and structural equation modeling was used to test the hypotheses. The results showed that innovation in services and marketing has a significant impact on tourist attitudes, marketing promotion, and destination performance. The results also show that the mediating role of marketing promotion on the impact of innovation on destination performance has not been confirmed.

KEY WORDS: Innovation - Marketing - Tourism - Tourist Attitude - Destination Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, in most industries, the role of innovation factor is widely recognized as the main factor to gain competitive advantage and maintain competition and growth. Awareness of the importance of innovation in products and services as an engine for economic growth is counted as the latest phenomenon. (Rajapasarana and Hugh, 2017). It should be noted that the importance of understanding the merits of innovation is essential for services and is essential as an engine of economic growth due to global change (Koo and Liu, 2010). This concept has been explored through various approaches to product, process, market, and organization (Twain and Tominen, 2009). Increasing attention to innovation draws customers' attention to the value of existing products and services (Nibak and Jensen, 2012). Today, companies use a variety of innovations and other trends to survive in turbulent and dynamic global markets. Each of these trends increases the performance of organizations. (Greenstein 2008). Tourism is one of the fastest-growing sectors of the world today and has created many business opportunities. Many empirical studies have been conducted on new investments by founders in the field of tourism (Puzi and Ismail, 2017).

Innovation in tourism is more complicated than other industries, and dynamism is another factor that is considered more important in the tourism industry than in other industries. Based on the available literature, the application of control mechanisms for managing the effectiveness of innovation in this industry can be analyzed. (Kallmuenzer and Peters, 2018). Today, in the tourism industry, the marketing content features of websites have significantly led to the effective delivery of messages, the quality of products and services, and the image created of their brand in the field of tourism and hospitality. Since the purpose of many such websites is to innovate in services, to raise people's awareness of the destination, and as a critical source of information, it plays an essential role in communicating between processes that take place abroad. (Lunt et al., 2010).

Organizations need new ideas and approaches to survive in today's turbulent and changing world. Increasing threats, on the one hand, and the use of opportunities, on the other, in a tense and unpredictable environment, are challenging organizations to face the ups and downs of change and innovation.

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2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Innovation is a strategic tool for sustaining business life and achieving a competitive advantage in the global marketplace (Karabulut, 2015). Unlike mass production and marketing activities, innovation activities involve a long process that is fraught with uncertainty and is likely to fail (Manso, 2011; Chamanor and Tian, 2018).

Innovation is getting out of the box and framework to create solutions and implement them (Chen et al., 2015). In general, innovation involves engaging a product with the right appearance to improve performance to provide new services (Oh and Theo¹, 2010; Froude et al., 2016). Based on the Oslo Manual (2005), four types of innovation are introduced, including product, process, organization, and marketing (Deloitte, 2017). Product and service innovation is the introduction of new goods and services that have significantly improved their features or methods of use (Henard et al., 2001). The purpose of product and service innovation is that the company can create a competitive advantage by introducing a new product or service that allows it to increase demand and increase sales prices. Product and service innovation can be measured by criteria such as increasing the quality of current products and services, developing new products and services (Rajabalipour, 2015). To expand the quality of new products or services, reliability, innovation compared to competitors, product and service innovation increase overall performance (Rosli & Sidek, 2014). Marketing innovation can be described as the ability of a company to dream of market and marketing, use communication channels and provide products and services to potential or existing customers (Gupta & et al., 2016). Marketing innovation is defined as continuous improvement in design, location, advertising, product, and pricing (marketing mix), new sales channels, market segmentation, advertising, new pricing strategy, market research, and marketing information systems (Muddaha & et al., 2018). Marketing innovation is the new implementation of the marketing method, which includes important changes in packaging and design, product and service placement, service promotion and pricing. Marketing innovation is measured on the basis of criteria such as designing new products and services through changes in its presentation and appearance, renewal of service channels, renewal of pricing methods of services and products and causes innovation in services and products (Rajabalipour, 2015). Marketing innovation is seen as the sum of the changes introduced by a company. Therefore, marketing innovation performance can be in two ways: 1- Introducing new marketing strategies, in the form of packaging, pricing or promotional offers, and 2- Improving marketing performance in terms of increasing customer satisfaction, sales and profitability (Modaha et al., 2018).

Ritsamer et al. (2016) in an article entitled "Study of the mediating role of tourist attitude towards the destination" with structural equation modeling method showed that the effect of attractiveness and innovation of the destination on attachment (tourist attitude) and tourist destination performance is significant. Attractiveness of the destination means access, facilities, landscape and local community that affects the attitude of tourists. Experimental findings provide valuable information to destination managers and policymakers on how to use destination perception and cognitive reinforcement to increase attachment and attitude toward the destination.

Lita et al., (2019) in an article entitled "Combining Capability of Knowledge in SMEs Related to Tourism in Indonesia: Does Marketing Innovation Modify the Relationship between Innovation and Product Performance?" It has a significant impact on service innovation. The results also showed that marketing innovation and service innovation have a significant impact on performance. In a paper entitled "The Relationship between Innovation Capability, Type of Innovation and Company Performances", Rajapasirana and Hugh (2018) examined the relationship between innovation capability and its types with company performance using correlation method. The results showed that there is a relationship between organizational innovation ability, types of innovation, process, product and marketing (and performance in the company and the effect of this relationship is positive).

Aksoy (2017) in an article entitled "Innovation culture, Innovation in Marketing and how Product Innovation Affect Corporate Market Performance?" Structural equation modeling has shown that innovation in marketing and product innovation has a significant impact on market performance. Hogan and Coote, (2014) in an article entitled "Organizational culture, innovation, and performance: A test of Schein's model", using Regression model examined the impact of innovation on company's performance. The findings generally support hypothesized relationships. The key conclusion is how layers of organizational culture, especially norms, artwork, and innovative behaviors, are partly the effects of values that support innovation in measuring company's performance. Theoretical and practical findings, especially in connection with the creation of an organizational culture, have shown that professional services reinforce innovative behavior. Shaukat et al. (2013) in a study entitled "Effects of Innovation Types on Firm Performance: an Empirical Study on Pakistan's Manufacturing Sector" with the method of correlation and regression examined the effect of different types of innovation on company performance. The results showed that different types of innovation (organizational, process, product and marketing) are related to each other and to the performance of innovation, and

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the effect of this relationship is positive. Financial performance is positive. Production performance is also positively related to market performance.

Yeh et al. (2019) in an article entitled "The Relationships among Experiential Marketing, Service Innovation, and Customer Satisfaction—A Case Study of Tourism Factories in Taiwan" showed by modeling structural equations that the impact of marketing on innovation in services is positive. Also, experiential marketing and service innovation have positive effects on tourist satisfaction. Karimova, (2020) in a paper entitled "The role of marketing services in the development of tourism innovation" with meta-analytical approach to the important points of marketing services and pointed to the innovative advances of tourism activities in various analyses.

Strong relationships between corporate innovation activities and their marketing capabilities have been proven to improve customer performance. In addition, the benefits of marketing innovation can be seen in increased product innovation. (Ngo & O'Cass, 2012). Marketing innovation can increase the competitiveness of incremental products through its ability to create new customers as a new product as innovation. Through innovation, companies achieve more efficient resource efficiency and produce the right products that can offset the costs involved and increase performance. Innovation can be broadly divided into process factor and product, as innovation brings not only technological change but also new product design. Process innovation can offset the costs of the process, as companies use new technology to solve problems, as well as reduce resource utilization and thus reduce energy consumption. These measures reduce costs, and they increase the company's performance. (Hoo et al., 2017; Becker & Egger, 2013).

Given the theoretical foundations and background of the research presented, this study claims that:

Hypothesis 1: Marketing innovation has a significant impact on service innovation.

Hypothesis 2 - Innovation of services has a significant effect on the attitude of tourists.

Hypothesis 3: Marketing innovation has a significant impact on the attitude of the tourist.

Innovation of products and services is very important for the promotion of industry and its competitiveness. It is responsible for supporting marketing and organizational innovations that provide new effective ways to promote new products and services and introduce flexible changes and flexibility in the management of companies in response to new markets and customer needs. (Camisón & Villar-López, 2014). Danneels & Kleinschmidt (2001) examined the concept of service innovation in a study. They found that the most common definition of service innovation is its creativity. Garcia & Calantone (2002) define innovation at the service and product level as a measure of the potential discontinuity that a product (process or service) can generate in technological marketing processes and enhance the marketing process (Story & et al., 2015). Marketing innovation can be described as the ability to participate in a market and marketing approach, use communication channels, and provide products and services to potential or existing customers (Gupta & et al., 2016). According to existing literature, marketing innovation is effective in continuously improving design, location, advertising, product and pricing (marketing mix), new sales channels, market segmentation, advertising, new pricing strategy, market research and marketing information systems. Marketing innovation is examined in terms of new marketing strategies and tactical measures, changes in design or packaging, sales or distribution, and changes in advertising and exhibitions, all of which are mainly to help companies in marketing related to new markets and Creating more attractive products or services and better performance is effective (Muddaha & et al., 2018).

In an article titled "Innovation of Rural Tourism Marketing Strategy" in a review, Shen (2019) showed that how to conduct rural tourism marketing and increase the popularity of rural tourism has become a top priority. This research proposes a strategy for promoting tourism and innovation in marketing and creates a business image in marketing. Batala et al., (2019) in a study entitled "National Development Policies, Tourism Innovation and Marketing: A Case Study of Nepal's Tourism Restrictions" by use of structural equation modeling created innovation in tourism and tourism marketing Strategies and they developed and promoted the tourism industry for a country. This article focuses on innovation and marketing, focusing on the discourse of Nepal's restrictions on the development and promotion of tourism. The results showed that the lack of cooperation between key stakeholders, the breakdown of common knowledge in key stakeholders, the inefficiency of the supreme council of tourism, insufficient budget, lack of skilled manpower, poor tourism infrastructure, lack of air services and non-updated global tourism policies have has weakened the tourism industry. (Batala et al., 2019). The tourists' attitude acts as a necessary and sufficient intermediary variable between their perceived attractiveness to a destination and the formation of destination attachment, and in fact, the tourists' attitude plays an important role in improving the performance of the destination. Also, after the formation of the attitude, as a facilitating factor, it increases the connection of tourists with a destination. The destination attractiveness affects the tourists' attitude and connects the tourist with the tourists' destination. (Ritsamer et al., 2016). In fact, attitude is the tourist's psychological orientation with its positive or negative evaluation of an object or experience, and attitude towards the destination describes the psychological tendencies that tourists express through their positive or negative evaluation of a destination

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experience and this improves the destination performance (Lee, 2009). According to the presented materials, this research claims that:

Hypothesis 4: Innovation of services has a significant effect on marketing promotion.

Hypothesis 5 - Marketing innovation has a significant impact on marketing promotion.

Hypothesis 6- Tourist attitude has a significant effect on marketing promotion.

Performance is one of the most discussed topics in the field of management literature, and since it is a complex and multidimensional concept, several definitions have been proposed. For example, Malichova and Durisova (2015) believe that performance is a tool that helps businesses to manage more effectively and achieve the company's goals. On the other hand, Yıldız et al. (2014) emphasize that business performance is a description of the achievement of goals based on the output obtained at the end of a trading period. Regardless of how performance is defined, measuring this concept is a necessary condition for ensuring the progress of a business in line with the appointed goals (Karaye et al., 2014). Suppliers often make significant efforts to collect feedback, predicting that it will improve service improvement and innovation. Participating in service innovation in response to customer dissatisfaction should provide several benefits to the supplier. This increases productivity by controlling costs and improved capabilities, and by increasing productivity and increasing quality, it improves and enhances performance (Ashok et al., 2018). Casais et al., (2020) in an article entitled " Tourism innovation through relationship marketing and value co-creation: A study on peer-to-peer online platforms for sharing accommodation", through in-depth interviews, made innovations in tourism through relationship marketing and the common value that tourists feel at the destination. Based on the results, value was created among tourists and the results showed that during the stay of tourists, close contact with guests were established. This fact is very important for creating a simultaneous tourism experience and increasing innovation in destination services. Liu, Y., (2017) in a review article entitled "Network Marketing Innovation and Management Construction of Tourism Market in China." with a review-based method showed that the tourism marketing network effectively demonstrates the tourism potential of tourists, improves the quality of tourism products, and creates a brand of modern tourism services and good performance at the destination. This article provides an example of the innovation and strategy of network marketing management in the Chinese tourism market.

According to the presented materials, this research claims that:

Hypothesis 7- Innovation of services has a significant effect on the performance of the destination.

Hypothesis 8: Marketing innovation has a significant impact on destination performance.

Hypothesis 9: Marketing promotion has a significant impact on destination performance.

The conceptual research model is based on the research hypotheses as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Research Model

The research method and the type of study are directly related to the purpose of the research and the choice of method depends on the nature of the subject, its goals, assumptions and executive possibilities. Given the main purpose, this research is practical. The method used is the analysis method based on structural equation modeling. The purpose of applied research is to develop applied knowledge in a specific field. In other words, applied research is directed towards the scientific application of knowledge. The sample includes visitors who visit historical places in Tehran. This city is known as the most important tourism destination in Iran. Moreover, it has 890 public registered historical places and monuments. The tourism facilities and amenities attract local and international tourists' attention toward this city. Therefore, Tehran is considered a case study in this paper. Due to the

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unlimited number of tourists, using the Karaj-Morgan sample size determination table, 384 tourists were determined as the sample size. These individuals were selected using a simple random sampling method.

In this research, the library method (articles, internet texts, books, etc.) was used for the theoretical dimension and the required information was extracted through a questionnaire and data collection in the research field. The present research questionnaire is from Lita et al.'s (2019) research, which has 5 product innovation indicators, 5 marketing innovation indicators and 8 destination performance indicators, as well as Ritsamer et al.'s (2016) research, which has 4 tourism attitude indicators and Batala et al.'s research. (2019), which has 3 marketing promotion indicators, has been used. Because these questions in the relevant articles have higher factor loads, and as a result, have more favorable validity and reliability. In this research respondents answered the questions of the questionnaire in a five-part spectrum from completely opposite = 1 to completely agree = 5.

The collected data were entered into Excel software for classification and entered into SPSS software for testing. First, the reliability of the questions was confirmed using the Cronbach's alpha test, and then the normality of the data distribution was confirmed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Then, using confirmatory factor analysis in SMART-PLS software, the validity (validity) of the questionnaire questions was confirmed, and finally, using structural equation modeling, we tested the hypotheses and confirmed the general model. It should be noted that the reliability of the questions in the total questionnaire was 0.954 and because it is more than 0.7, the reliability was confirmed.

3. RESULTS

In the descriptive section for data analysis, descriptive statistical techniques are used to examine how the statistical sample responds to the main research variables.

Table 1: Numerical criteria of the main research variables

Product/Service Innovation	Marketing Innovation	Tourist Attitude	Marketing Improvement	Destination Performance	
3.6129	3.5378	3.6440	3.7677	3.5816	Average
.77084	.72840	.71775	.70488	.69438	Standard Deviation
.594	.531	.515	.497	.482	Variance
-.774	-.536	-.407	-.480	-.254	Skewness
1.176	.861	.812	.804	.287	Kurtosis

As can be seen, the highest average is related to marketing promotion and the lowest average is related to marketing innovation. It should be noted that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for the final study of data distribution.

Table 2: Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normality of research variables

Product/Service Innovation	Marketing Innovation	Tourist Attitude	Marketing Improvement	Destination Performance	
.106	.089	.093	.128	.058	Statistical hypothesis testing
.000 ^c	.000 ^c	.000 ^c	.000 ^c	.003 ^c	Statistical significance (P-value)

According to the significance level of the above table, all of which are 0.000 and less than 0.05, so the data distribution is significantly different from the normal distribution and as a result, the data distribution is not normal and we can test the hypotheses and the general model. Use the path analysis test in smart-pls software because this software is not sensitive to data distribution and also analyzes abnormal data.

The conceptual model as follows in the following two cases of standard coefficients and Statistical significance is as follows:

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Figure 2: Route parameters of the conceptual research model

As can be seen in the chart above, all routes except the one between the tourist attitudes to marketing improvement and destination performance they have a good significance level because they are more than 1.96. The values of divergent and convergent validity, as well as the combined reliability and Cronbach are as follows:

Table 3: Coefficients of External Research Model

Cronbach's alpha	AVE	CR	t-value	Factor Loading	Questions	
0.84	0.62	0.89	8.17	0.77	1-Promotion of products / New services with different technical and functional specifications than the existing ones.	Product innovation
			22.96	0.83	2-Increasing the value of the product / service	
			24.11	0.85	3- Promotion of main products / services	
			17/17	0.80	4-Adjoining new elements to products / services	
			8.62	0.69	5-Promotion of innovation in current products to improve the ease of use for tourists and increase tourist satisfaction	
0.84	0.60	0.88	16.32	0.77	6-Correction and development of general marketing management activities	Marketing Innovation
			12.22	0.75	7-Renovation of distribution channels without changing the legal processes related to product submission / service delivery	
			12.11	0.75	8-Modernization of product / service pricing techniques used to price current products / services or new products / services	
			22.22	0.81	9-Modify current product / service plans or new products / services by making changes	
			22.26	0.80	10- New techniques in product / service marketing	
0.78	0.61	0.86	18.61	0.81	11- It creates good feeling about this trip	Tourism Attitude
			22.43	0.82	12- This trip is satisfying for me.	
			9.85	0.73	13- This trip gives me a positive feeling.	
			12.41	0.76	14- I love this trip and it's fun for me.	
0.79	0.70	0.87	14.85	0.81	15- The use of digital technology in marketing	Marketing Improvement
			23.89	0.86	16- Use collaboration and partnership-based marketing	
			18.96	0.83	17- Segmentation of target market based on customers	
0.90	0.60	0.92	8.24	0.64	18- Flexibility and volume of provided services	

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		12.14	0.79	19- The quality of services provided in accordance with existing standards	Destination Performance
		9.77	0.67	20- Speed of provided services	
		19.78	0.79	21-Market share	
		21.32	0.81	22-Technologic Competition	
		21.33	0.82	23- Renovation of the management system and the company's vision along with changing the company's environment	
		22.99	0.84	24-Innovations introduced for work processes and methods	
		26.82	0.86	25-Number of projects related to new products and services	

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the research findings, it is suggested to improve the level of service innovation by developing new services with different technical and functional specifications, by adding new methods of providing services and by developing innovation in existing services to improve the ease of use of services for tourists, because according to the research results, this leads to a positive attitude of the tourist, promotion of marketing and performance of the destination. It is suggested to improve the level of marketing innovation by reforming and expanding public marketing management activities, updating distribution channels without changing the legal processes associated with service delivery, modernizing service pricing techniques, modifying existing service plans or new services through new marketing techniques in services, because it ultimately improves the destination performance. It is also suggested to consider the desirability of tourists' attitudes by creating a positive, satisfying and enjoyable feeling of travel among tourists. Based on the findings, to improve the level of marketing it is recommended to use digital technology in marketing, using marketing based on cooperation and partnership, as well as segmenting the target market based on customers. It is suggested to achieve the desired and appropriate performance at the destination by expanding and flexibility in the volume of services provided, by providing services in accordance with the quality of existing standards, fast service delivery, increasing market share, technological competition as well as modernization of management system and firm's perspective along with changing its environment and increasing the number of projects, related to recent services. At the end of the research, the researcher will identify new perspectives that can guide researchers who intend to do similar research in the future, so the following suggestions are for future research:

- Evaluate the role of different types of innovation to attract tourists.
- Identifying and prioritizing the factors affecting the innovative destination performance with a tourist-oriented approach.
- Identifying and prioritizing the factors that reduce the level of financial and non-financial performance of tourism.
- Investigating the effect of innovation on performance of destination innovation by mediation of organizational innovation, process innovation, product innovation and marketing innovation in tourism.
- Investigating the effect of innovation performance on financial performance with the mediating role of tourist attitude.
- Developing a tourism model with a marketing innovation approach using qualitative and quantitative combined research.

Undoubtedly, any research faces a series of inherent shortcomings and limitations. Some of the limitations of the research are as follows:

- The limitation of time and cost allocation of the researcher has been effective in presenting and feedback of the results of the research and has not provided the possibility of a more comprehensive study of the research model.
- Lack of full access to all information.
- The existence of a spatial domain makes the research results generalizable to the same spatial domain and not to another.

5. CONCLUSION

Examining the role of innovation in the tourist attitude and improving the destination performance, we concluded that the innovation of services and marketing have a significant impact on the tourist attitude, marketing promotion and destination performance. The results also show that the mediating role of marketing promotion has not been confirmed in the impact of innovation on destination performance. The results of route analysis showed that innovation in services has a greater impact on tourist attitude, marketing promotion and destination performance with coefficients of 0.525, 0.563 and 0.726, respectively than marketing innovation on tourist attitude, marketing promotion and destination performance with coefficients of 0.481, 0.452 and 0.311. It is worth noting that innovation in services and marketing has a significant impact directly on the tourist attitude,

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marketing promotion and destination performance, while indirectly it does not have a significant impact on marketing promotion and destination performance and rejects the mediating role. In general, it can be said that the conceptual model presented in the present study consists of three separate models, which are service innovation and marketing innovation in all three common models. In these three models, the mediating role of service innovation has been confirmed. It is a good medium for the impact of marketing innovation on tourist attitudes, marketing promotion and destination performance. Also, the overall fit of the GOF model, which is obtained from the geometric mean of the explained variance index R² and the quality of measurement model of COMMUNALITY, is equal to 0.7 and because it is more than 0.36, has a desirable amount. According to Table 3, divergent narrative values showed that all coefficients were greater than 0.4 and were desirable. The values for convergent validity also show that the desired values are greater than 0.5. Also, the combined reliability and Cronbach's alpha have the desired values of more than 0.7, which as a result the validity and reliability of the questionnaire has been examined and confirmed. Also, the R² multiplier coefficients have the desired values higher than 0.35 and show that, the independent variables in the model generally can significantly predict and explain the dependent variables. The fit results of the model showed that the quality of the COMMUNALITY measurement model also has the desired values above 0.5.

RESOURCES

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APPENDIX

Cronbachs Alpha

	Cronbachs Alpha
Product/Service Innovation	0.849985
Marketing Innovation	0.840907
Tourism Attitude	0.789120
Marketing Improvement	0.790451
Destination Performance	0.904472

Latent Variable Correlations

	Latent Correlations	Variable	Latent Correlations	Variable	Latent Correlations	Variable	Latent Correlations	Variable
Product/Service Innovation	1.000000							
Marketing Innovation	0.727014		1.000000					
Tourism Attitude	0.598156		0.780257		1.000000			
Marketing Improvement	0.435325		0.548002		0.644135		1.000000	
Destination Performance	0.635279		0.855073		0.876244		0.653964	

	Destination Performance
Product/Service Innovation	
Marketing Innovation	
Tourism Attitude	
Marketing Improvement	
Destination Performance	1.000000

R Square

	R Square
Product/Service Innovation	0.546470
Marketing Innovation	
Tourism Attitude	0.881412
Marketing Improvement	0.785053
Destination Performance	0.923868

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AVE

	AVE
Product/Service Innovation	0.627540
Marketing Innovation	0.609006
Tourism Attitude	0.612716
Marketing Improvement	0.704956
Destination Performance	0.603539

Communality

	communality
Product/Service Innovation	0.627540
Marketing Innovation	0.609006
Tourism Attitude	0.612716
Marketing Improvement	0.704956
Destination Performance	0.603539

Composite Reliability

	Composite Reliability
Product/Service Innovation	0.893393
Marketing Innovation	0.886110
Tourism Attitude	0.863292
Marketing Improvement	0.877520
Destination Performance	0.923425

	communality	R Square	GOF
Product/Service Innovation	0.627540	0.546470	0.7
Marketing Innovation	0.609006		
Tourism Attitude	0.612716	0.881412	
Marketing Improvement	0.704956	0.785053	
Destination Performance	0.603539	0.923868	
Average	0.626	0.783	

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